

Contributions to Succession in a Family Business from the Perspective of Global University Entrepreneurial Spirit Students' Survey (GUESSS)

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Abstract

Relationship between family support and organizational commitment is investigated, in the attitude of succession in a family business, and, this one, in the succession intention. Therefore, the research operationalizes constructs studied by the Global University Entrepreneurial Spirit Students' Survey, in a survey with 289 university students from the Federal University in Brazil. Structural modeling showed satisfactory adjustment indices to support the seven hypotheses of the study: family support assumes an important explanatory capacity for the variation of affective commitment ($R^2=38\%$), as well as of normative commitment ($R^2=41\%$); commitment (affective and normative) assumes an important explanatory capacity for the variation in the succession attitude ($R^2=49\%$); and, the suggested relationship between the succession attitude and the succession intention ($\beta=0.775$; $t=22.772$, $p=0.000$), in addition to being supported, demonstrates the greater explanatory capacity of the predictor construct variation ($R^2=60\%$). It was concluded, therefore, that prior planning, with actions that mobilize future family members (successors) can result in the achievement of the longevity of these companies.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, family business, intention of succession, family succession, GUESSS

1. Introduction

Family businesses represent a dominant organizational form in the world (Daspit, Holt, Chrisman, & Long, 2015), being a model in which the ownership and control of the business belong to family members, with the possibility of transfer between generations (Kiwia, Bengesi, & Ndyetabula, 2020). It represents vector of economic development (Anggadwita, Profityo, Turipanam, & Lamanda, 2020), while they mean about 80% of all businesses, with contribution of 70-80% to the gross domestic product (GDP) in many countries (Poza & Daugherty, 2013, Family Firm Institute, 2017), in particular, 80% of firms in Brazil, which are Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) (Volpato, Viera, Zilli, & Santos, 2018), and participation between 50 and 70% of formal jobs in the world (Kiwia, Bengesi, & Ndyetabula, 2020).

Theorizations on the configuration of family businesses seek to make explicit contributions from the perspective of longevity, in studies on interactions between family, business and ownership (Gersick et al., 1997), which is observed since Christensen (1953), Trow (1961), Sharma (1997), considered seminal. While the succession process represents a critical moment in this business model (Lansberg & Astrachn, 1994; Lansberg, 1998, 1999), accompanied by managerial challenges and obstacles involving family histories (Oliveira, Albuquerque, & Pereira, 2013), Sharma, Chua and Chrisman (1997, 2001), elucidate factors that influence succession planning and Sharma, Chrisman and Chua (2003), advance the understanding of determinants of satisfaction with the process (subjective) and the effectiveness of succession (objective).

The succession process also derives from (i) organizational implications (strategy, organization and culture,

governance and performance) and (ii) drives (intergenerational family dynamics, managerial style and personality of the CEO, organizational and market context) (Miller, Steier, & Le Breton-Miller, 2003), while aspects that challenge their success trigger attention to the understanding of the entrepreneurial face involved (Porfirio, Felício, & Carrilho, 2020), or managerial, from the perspective of economic and financial management of business, which weakens the effectiveness of the enterprise (Pinto & Souza, 2009).

Against the backdrop of the economic and social relevance of family businesses, their mortality is high (De Jesus, Machado, & De Jesus, 2009), while about 30% go beyond the first generation, passing to 10% and 15% those that manage to go to the third, and, finally, only 3% manage to survive until the fourth generation (Stamm & Lubinski, 2011; Mokhber, Rasid, Vakilbashi, Zamil, & Seng, 2017). In this horizon, succession challenges tension movements favorable to business sustainability (Evert et al., 2016; Short et al., 2016), on the way to overcome the conservative profile generally present in generational dispute, which limit innovation (Kraus, Pohjola, & Koponen, 2012), with attachment to the past, fear of the future and maladaptation are at the confluence of these conflicts (Miller, Steier, & Le Breton-Miller, 2003).

Whereas the choice of succession by a family member involves beliefs and confidence in their abilities, which defines the intrafamily dynamics fundamental to the successor's self-perception (De Massis, Chua, & Chrisman, 2008), the learnings experienced directly with the incumbent (Martínez-Sanchis, Aragón-Amonarriz, & Iturrioz-Landart, 2020), to understanding family and business culture. These are movements that direct the succession process, in relation to the vision, intentions and behaviors of the actors involved (Porfirio, Felício, & Carrilho, 2020).

In this context, it is observed the relevance of family dynamics for succession in family businesses (Dawson, Sharm, Irving, Marcus, & Chirico, 2015), since when the successor is prepared by the founders, the process is more effective (Kiwia, Bengesi, & Ndyetabula, 2020). In this sense, research shows that investment in formal education of heirs and moral support from family members contribute to the organization's performance (Porfirio, Felício, & Carrilho, 2020), although financial support has been identified with a negative relationship (Welsh & Kaciak, 2019), possibly related to a lower commitment developed with the business, since this involvement seems to motivate family members to stay in the business, as well as success criteria (Zahra, Hayton, Neubaum, Dibrell, & Craig, 2008). Simultaneously, family support (preparation) and the development of commitments can be associated with succession intentions, which, in turn, mobilize action toward the future of the family enterprise (Carsrud & Bränback, 2011). Given the above, the research aims to investigate relationships between family (parental) support (instrumental assistance and verbal encouragement) and organizational commitment (normative and affective), in the attitude of succession in family business, as well as the relationship of this intending to succession. For this, the Global University Entrepreneurial Spirit Students' Survey (GUESSS) was used, carried out in a Brazilian Federal University, for operationalizing, in its questionnaire, the constructs of the relations of this research.

With the analyses based on the study of the relations among the constructs, the research aims to deepen the understanding of the contribution of family dynamics in relation to family succession vis-à-vis the company's sustainability throughout the generational transitions through the mobilization of attitudes and intentions of continuity of the family business by successors. Thus, it is derived, with the discussion, contributions regarding the preservation of family capital (Martin-Cruz et al., 2020), from the perspective of longevity and, consequently, contributions to economic and social development.

2. Succession in Family Businesses

Understanding family businesses involves defining their constitutive elements; family, company and entrepreneurial family (Brandt, Scheffer, & Gallon, 2020). According to Passos et al. (2006), family involves a social group united by biological, legal and/or affinity bonds that is constantly changing, with its own inclusion, qualification, recognition and assessment criteria, thus including direct descendants, spouses and cohabitants; the entrepreneurial family, on the other hand, assumes bonds arising from heritage and legacy, capable of committing to the challenge of adding value for the next generations.

Thus, the family business starts from the combination between economic-financial objectives, like any other business, and non-economic objectives, which come from the family's participation in the company, so that the figures of family, owners and management overlap (Tagiuri & Davis, 1996). Bornholdt (2005), on the other hand, considers a series of fundamentals to identify a family business, among them; the shareholding control belongs to one of them, the blood ties determine the succession, the relatives find themselves in strategic positions and the organization's values merge with those of the family.

Furthermore, identifying a company as family owned assumes the existence of at least two generations in the

context of business management (Volpato et al., 2018), without the size being a relevant criterion for analyzing its challenges, since small, medium and large family businesses present similar challenges (Matias, 2004), while the succession to be deduced from the course of evolution of the entrepreneurial family is a process of greater relevance (Lansberg & Astrachn, 1994, Lansberg, 1998, 1999). Without the generational succession transition, we have an entrepreneurial company, given the coexistence still with the first generation, that is, its founder (Matias, 2004).

Favorable aspects to family succession reveal the contribution of intra-family dynamics in the path of trust strengthened by bonds and affective ties, as well as values of the pro-business family institution culture, that is, with the recognition of skills, efficiency, dedication and loyalty (Lima, 2016; Zambarda & Vortmann, 2020; Brandt, Scheffer, & Gallon, 2020). In line with the entrepreneurial dream of the founder, a culture permeated by consensus around the growth and continuation of the business is perpetuated (Lodi, 1994), which imposes family relationships in which family and business culture are mixed (Frugis, 2007), in identities guided by credibility, leadership, charisma, and perseverance (Ricca, 2012). The legacy of the founder, therefore, should be conducted with technique and wisdom by the successor knowing how to benefit from histories and paths traveled (Werner, 2004).

The succession is challenged by power games and political disputes, which overshadow the managerial capacity and economic-financial management necessary for performance (Pinto & Souza, 2009; Flores & Grisci, 2012; Freitas & Frezza, 2005). The configuration of family relationships governs the succession process, while the founders' influence can be either favorable, when prior planning enables the successor to develop for the position; or unfavorable, when the rupture process expresses interpersonal and/or generational conflicts, and weakens the company's identity based on the legacy of its founder (Carmo, Kendler, & Murta, 2017).

The process of transition of power between generations, therefore, can be planned (with a focus on adaptation) and abrupt (with disruptions) (Leone, 1991; Ballinger & Marcel, 2010). Whereas unpredictable factors, such as the successor's death, the logic of succession planning imprints the vulnerability of business concentration in the figure of the founding entrepreneur (Volpato et al., 2018). In this case, planning privileges the necessary training for the successor to continue the business, as well as communication about the responsibilities inherent to the performance (Volpato et al., 2018), which the organizational and administrative structure can support the process, minimizing challenges associated with the focus of the future vision (Vancil, 1987; Werner, 2004). Succession, from a planning perspective, can result in an opportunity to realign organizational strategies (Miller, Le Breton-Miller, & Scholnick, 2008).

From the successor's perspective, cherishing the business contributes to the transition, as does a respectful relationship between the people involved (Bernhoeft, 1987). Having knowledge, skills and attitudes developed in formal and informal education processes, in a context of family harmony, also favor the success of the process, which should have a plan with well-defined objective events (Lodi, 1998; Santos et al., 2017; Souza, Brito, & Alvareli, 2011).

It should be guaranteed, by the successor, the credibility and legitimacy developed by the founder, particularly, among suppliers, customers and employees (Frugis, 2007). In this case, successor (receiving the baton) and successor (passing the baton) share the movement of perpetuating the company's logic, which requires alignment and willingness of members in relation to the new roles assumed (Ganefri & Sidek, 2013; Weismeier-Sammer & Hatak, 2014). This alignment, activated by trust in the parties, also involves family and organizational culture which, in the context of knowledge sharing, will be favored (Davenport & Prusak, 1998; Terra, 2005; Trevinyo & Taipés, 2010).

In the scope of transition, successor training involves the sharing of knowledge, practices, and experiences of the successor, understood as family (parental) support given to the preparation of the process. With support from Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory, Turner et al., (2003), through the development of a support scale, understands this support for the development of perceived self-efficacy, particularly triggered through instrumental support (development of career-related skills), career modeling (provision of professional behaviors), social/verbal persuasion (encouraging and evaluating educational and professional development), and emotional stimulation/support (support and affection one receives as a result of professional development).

From the perspective of Bandura (1997) and Turner et al. (2003), in family dynamics it is parents who are the main activators of experiences, understanding parental support from the perspective of instrumental support, career modeling, verbal encouragement and emotional support contribute to perceived self-efficacy. Moreover, self-efficacy is also evidenced as a predictor of social (Anderson & Betz, 2001) and college efficacy (Solberg, O'Brien, Villareal, Kennel, & Davis, 1993).

On the other hand, from this support derives the bond of the individual with the family business, as well as with the community in which the company is inserted (Cabrera-Suárez, SaáPérez, & García Almeida, 2001). Commitment, in this case, emerges as an energy (or state of mind) that mobilizes the individual to act towards a given target (Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001), while commitment levels are positively related to succession success as a result of the commitment to the family business (Sharma, 1997).

From the perspective of Meyer and Allen's (1991) model of commitment to the organization, an individual can develop three different types of commitment: the instrumental, the normative, and the affective. The affective base derives from emotional ties and positive experiences related to the target organization of the commitment, with behaviors expressed in the form of loyalty, respect, admiration, pleasure, voluntarism, and zeal for the company (Silva, 2008); The normative base, in turn, involves the sense of obligation to a given context that imposes strong moral rules for action, which generally represses behavior that does not adhere to the established rules, suggesting the awakening of the sense of guilt and duty, as mobilizes behaviors of continuity in the organization by obligation (Siqueira & Gomide, 2004); the instrumental base, finally, involves analysis of opportunities (or lack of alternatives) and rational analysis to the economic benefits of the relationship with the organization. In the instrumental (or calculating) perspective, it would also trigger, according to Siqueira and Gomide (2004), low motivation and low performance in the company.

In the family succession process, the study by Sharma and Irving (2005) discusses the contribution of commitment, in the sense of analyzing how each base influences the pro-succession movement. The discussion points to the idea of a commitment structure that mobilizes the involvement of potential successors toward the family business, while they conclude the direct influence of affective (desire-based), normative (obligation-based), and instrumental (cost avoidance-based) commitments on the behaviors of successor members (Sharma & Irving, 2005).

Along these lines, the study of Dawson, Sharm, Irving, Marcus, and Chirico (2015), with support in the studies of Tajfel and Turner (1985), Miller and Le-Breton Miller (2006), Salvato, Minichilli, and Piccarreta (2012), Lumpkin, Martin, and Vaughn (2008), Chirico, Sirmon, Sciascia, and Mazzola, (2011) and Vallejo and Langa (2010), analyze antecedents of commitment from the perspective of family succession and, although all bases influence the process, the results indicated that affective and normative commitment were positively associated with the intention to continue the family business. Regarding affective commitment, the antecedents are the alignment of identity with the company from the perspective of pride in the legacy of the family history associated with the enterprise; and the alignment of career interests, which involves convergence of career interests with the work performed by the company. Regarding the normative commitment, the antecedents are the family expectations, which involves the influence of the set of norms, values and beliefs of the family and business culture on the behavior of its members; and the family orientation, which associates the value patterns of tradition and loyalty shared with the members and which are internalized and expressed in behaviors.

Thus, based on the constructs related to the parental support scale of Turner et al. (2003), "instrumental assistance and career modeling" and "verbal encouragement and emotional support", present in the University Entrepreneurial Spirit Students' Survey (GUESS), we hypothesize a positive relationship between family support (parental) and the successor's commitment to the family business. Thus, the hypotheses are derived:

Hypotheses 1 and 2 - Parental support positively influences commitment to success with business in the family firm

H1a - Instrumental assistance and career modeling positively influence affective commitment.

H1b - Instrumental assistance and career modeling positively influence normative commitment.

H2a - Verbal encouragement and emotional support positively influence affective commitment.

H2b - Verbal encouragement and emotional support positively influence normative commitment.

Regarding the consequences of the successors' commitment to the family business, it is considered that commitment mobilizes action (Sharma & Irving, 2005), while the decision to continue and contribute with the company is the result of attitudes and intentions in favor of this behavior. In this movement, Linan and Chen (2009), supported by the research of Baron (2004), Shaver and Scott (1991), Krueger, Reilly, and Carsrud (2000), Fayolle et al. (2006), Kolvereid, (1996), Bird (1988), Lee and Wong (2004), Boyd and Vozikis (1994), Tubbs and Ekeberg (1991), define that attitudes and intentions influence the decision, being these cognitive variables, then voluntary and conscious. In this context, based on the Theory of Planned Behavior, formulated by Ajzen (1991), they structure a model that explains entrepreneurial intention based on its antecedents, and considers intention, which mobilizes needs, values, beliefs, and habits, as fundamental to pro-business behavior.

In relation to the antecedents of entrepreneurial intention, Linan and Chen (2009) present situational factors and the beliefs and values related to attitude, whereas the latter explains intention. Personal attitude, in this case, refers to the personal evaluation, positive or negative, which encompasses the effect involved, but mainly evaluative considerations. Regarding the subjective norm antecedent, it is understood the influence of social pressures that mobilize the sense of obligation, mainly defined by reference persons who share values, later internalized as obligation. Regarding the antecedent perceived behavioral control, which is close to the idea of self-efficacy as defined by Badura (1997), it comprises the self-perception about the challenges, the potentialities, and the feasibility of being an entrepreneur, as well as about the ability to fulfill entrepreneurial attributions.

Thomas and Muller (2000) argue that an attitude can be considered as predetermined but changeable thoughts, feelings. Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) teach that attitude is a pre-disposition to respond, either favorably or unfavorably, to objects, people, institutions, or events. Fazio (1990) presents attitudes as an association between an object and an evaluation concerning this object, making a distinction between weak and strong attitudes, the strong ones being more quickly accessed from memory and also better predictors of behavior. They are therefore characteristics acquired over a lifetime (Ajzen, 2001).

Shook, Priem, and Mcgee (2003) define entrepreneurial intention as a conscious state of mind that precedes action and directs it toward the goal, which, in the case under review, is to create a business. For Shapero and Sokol (1982), three aspects mobilize intention: (i) perception of desirability; (ii) propensity to act; and (iii) perception of feasibility. Thompson (2009) and Krueger, Reilly, and Carsrud (2000) and Davidson (1995) define entrepreneurial intention from the perspective of conscious planning, or planned behavior, with concrete actions, around entrepreneurship, even if the realization depends on other environmental factors and personal events. The intention-based model, therefore, predicts pro-business behaviors with a coherent, parsimonious, generalizable, and robust theoretical support (Krueger, Reilly, & Carsrud, 2000).

In this path, to advance in the understanding of aspects favorable to succession in family businesses, the relationship between successor commitment and pro-business actions (Sharma & Irving, 2005) was inferred, these being the result of a positive or negative evaluation (attitude), which precedes the movement of a planned behavior (intention) (Linan & Chen, 2009) towards the decision to continue with the family enterprise. Both, constructs, were operationalized based on the succession attitude and intention scale, adapted from Linan and Chen (2009), present in the University Entrepreneurial Spirit Students' Survey (GUESS). Therefore, we have the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 3 - Commitment positively influences succession attitude in family business.

H3a - Affective commitment positively influences succession attitude.

H3b - Normative commitment positively influences the attitude towards succession.

Hypothesis 4 - Attitude towards succession in a family business positively influences succession intention.

3. Methodology

To investigate relationships between family (parental) support (instrumental assistance and verbal encouragement) and organizational commitment (normative and affective), intending to succession in a family business, as well as its relationship intending to succession, we undertook a quantitative study given the purpose of describing and inferring relationships through hypothesis testing, following the structural analysis procedure (Hair, Hult, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2014), according to the hypotheses presented in figure 1.

Figure 1. Hypothesized relationships model

Source: Prepared by the authors.

The study considers constructs operationalized through the international research project Global University Entrepreneurial Spirit Students' Survey (GUESSS), conducted at a Brazilian Federal University. This research aims to understand various aspects related to the entrepreneurial spirit, from aspects of culture, teaching conditions and support from the educational institution, behavioral determinants to information about the succession process.

That said, for this study, only the scale related to family succession was selected from the GUESSS questionnaire, gathered by its constructs (and variables), namely: "Instrumental Assistance and Career Modeling", "Verbal Encouragement and Emotional Support", "Affective Commitment", "Normative Commitment", "Succession Attitude" and "Succession Intention". The sample was defined based on college students who had previously informed that they were children of parents who are majority owners of a company, which generated a quantitative of 289 respondents in a single Brazilian Federal University.

The research hypotheses were assessed through the structural model, estimated by the Partial Least Squares Path Modeling [PLS-PM] method, based on covariance, whose choice was based on the possibility of testing relationships between latent variables without the assumption of multivariate normality (Hair et al., 2014), being also suitable for exploratory studies (Chin & Newsted, 1999). SmartPLS software (version 2.0 M3 Beta) was used for the analysis. Regarding the questionnaires, previous treatment indicated the existence of missing values; however, they were replaced by the mean, since they accounted for no less than 5% of the sample (Hair et al., 2014).

Even with the minimum attendance of 200 respondents (Kline, 2015), the statistical criteria of the sample quality were analyzed through the G*Power software, version (3.1.9.2), as suggested by Ringle, Silva, and Bido (2014) and Hair, Hult, Ringle, and Sarstedt (2017). To analyze the effect size, or effect size, which represents the index of the degree of deviation from the null hypothesis (Cohen, 1977), and the higher this value, the greater the degree to which the phenomenon under study is manifested. About the sample of 289 respondents, the tests were performed considering the effect size equal to 0.30, significance equal to 0.05 and number of predictors equal to 5 (represented by the largest number of structural arrows arriving at a latent variable), and to analyze power or potency ($1-\beta$ err prob).

For sample quality analysis the post hoc test, Linear Multiple Regression: fixed model, R^2 deviation from zero of the F tests family, was performed, this being the type of analysis that checks, whether the null hypothesis assumes the condition that the R^2 value is equal to zero or whether the alternative hypothesis assumes that R^2 is different from zero. To this end, we assumed power parameters of the f^2 effect: 35% (large) and significance of 5%, which resulted in power or power ($1-\beta$ err prob) equal to 1 (100%), with Critical F equal to 2.244, noncentrality parameter equal to 104.3 and denominator df equal to 292. For the sample collected, the statistical indicators reveal both its suitability and sufficiency for conducting the research (Faul et al., 2007; Ringle, Silva, & Bido, 2014).

4. Presentation of Results

The first step of structural equation modeling consisted of the analysis of the measurement model, which attests to the validity and reliability of the research constructs (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2017). At this point, the total valid sample of 289 respondents was used to assess the relationships.

Next, to evaluate the measurement model estimated by the Smart PLS 3 software, the correlations between the FLs (factor loading) and the factor loading (crossloading) were considered. Thus, tables 1 was extracted, which report the level of the FLs and indicators, respectively, through validity (convergent and discriminant) and reliability (alpha and composite).

In verifying the level of FLs, convergent validity, under the Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion, should present values of the average variance extracted (Average Variance Extracted- AVEs) greater than 0.50 ($AVE > 0.50$), that said, the latent variables "instrumental assistance", "normative commitment", "affective commitment", "succession attitude", "succession intention" and "verbal encouragement" explained more than half of the variance of their indicators.

Table 1. Correlation matrix between latent variables

	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Assistência_Modelagem	0,849					
2. Atitude_Sucesso	0,500	0,854				
3. Compromisso_Afetivo	0,514	0,648	0,869			
4. Compromisso_Normativo	0,589	0,676	0,767	0,817		
5. Encorajamento_Suporte	0,651	0,531	0,605	0,584	0,952	
6. Intençao_Sucesso	0,494	0,775	0,641	0,720	0,550	0,928
Alfa	0,923	0,906	0,919	0,827	0,826	0,967
AVE	0,721	0,729	0,756	0,667	0,905	0,862
CC	0,939	0,930	0,939	0,887	0,966	0,974

Key: Alpha: Cronbach's Alpha; AVE: Average Variance Extracted; CC: Reliability composite.

Note. Bold diagonal values are the square root of the average variance extracted.

The values on the diagonal are the square root of the AVE.

All correlations are significant at 1%.

From Table 1, the discriminant validity of the study is observed ($\sqrt{AVE} >$ Pearson correlations among constructs), based on Fornell and Larcker's (1981) criterion. Thus, all VLs shared greater variance with their indicators than with the other FLs, and were therefore independent of each other. And, regarding Reliability composite, the values estimated by the FLs, assumed values between $0.7 < CC < 0.95$ (being considered satisfactory) (Hair Jr. et al. 2014). Finally, it is stated that the measurement model, after the removal in three stages of variables Q11.6.2.2 (Load 0.283), Q11.6.2.1 (Load 0, 267) and Q11.6.2.3 (Load 0, 367), has internal consistency for the study constructs as a function of $\alpha > 0.7$, according to Hair Jr. et al. (2014).

Table 2. Factorial loadings matrix

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Q11.6.1_1	0,839	0,485	0,484	0,561	0,644	0,517
Q11.6.1_2	0,869	0,473	0,492	0,565	0,628	0,491
Q11.6.1_3	0,879	0,476	0,482	0,559	0,608	0,465
Q11.6.1_4	0,844	0,39	0,356	0,42	0,465	0,322
Q11.6.1_5	0,850	0,336	0,356	0,408	0,461	0,316
Q11.6.1_6	0,812	0,339	0,402	0,435	0,447	0,343
Q11.2.1.2_1	0,41	0,717	0,398	0,408	0,37	0,484
Q11.2.1.2_2	0,322	0,817	0,48	0,509	0,41	0,56
Q11.2.1.2_3	0,471	0,906	0,623	0,649	0,468	0,714
Q11.2.1.2_4	0,492	0,931	0,604	0,642	0,473	0,726
Q11.2.1.2_5	0,428	0,879	0,616	0,628	0,525	0,767
Q11.4.1_1	0,377	0,455	0,789	0,533	0,416	0,426
Q11.4.1_2	0,482	0,548	0,912	0,645	0,553	0,533
Q11.4.1_3	0,448	0,671	0,859	0,746	0,573	0,68
Q11.4.1_4	0,469	0,573	0,915	0,714	0,577	0,589
Q11.4.1_5	0,449	0,541	0,866	0,667	0,487	0,519
Q11.4.2_1	0,522	0,628	0,69	0,908	0,566	0,711
Q11.4.2_2	0,497	0,575	0,643	0,840	0,519	0,582
Q11.4.2_3	0,464	0,596	0,638	0,872	0,485	0,651
Q11.4.2_4	0,452	0,374	0,528	0,616	0,298	0,352
Q11.6.2_4	0,565	0,469	0,551	0,524	0,950	0,5
Q11.6.2_5	0,68	0,492	0,595	0,551	0,958	0,506
Q11.6.2_6	0,61	0,551	0,581	0,589	0,947	0,561
Q11.2.1.1_1	0,37	0,637	0,526	0,577	0,432	0,838
Q11.2.1.1_2	0,491	0,748	0,63	0,693	0,551	0,949
Q11.2.1.1_3	0,495	0,736	0,619	0,694	0,536	0,954
Q11.2.1.1_4	0,486	0,757	0,632	0,706	0,551	0,968
Q11.2.1.1_5	0,43	0,685	0,535	0,633	0,459	0,906
Q11.2.1.1_6	0,47	0,747	0,617	0,695	0,523	0,948

Source: research data.

Note. All factor loadings are significant at 1%.

Considering the analysis of the indicators, the convergent validity followed the criterion of factor loading greater than 0.7, being maintained the loading 0.616 not to harm the content validity of each latent variable of the study (Savelsbergh, Van Der Eijden, & Poell, 2009). Furthermore, for discriminant validity, it was observed that the factorial loading (in bold) are greater than the cross-loading (“off-diagonal” loading). Next, the factor loading of the model and the structural coefficients (β) of analysis were evaluated (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Factorial loadings and the structural coefficients (β) of the measurement model

Source: Research data.

Note. SmartPLS software output.

In the structural model, hypotheses 1, 2, 3 and 4 were evaluated by the path diagram, allowing rejection or not. Before evaluating the R2 of the model, the hypothesized relationships (Figure 2) were tested to verify the significance of the standardized coefficients (path coefficients) through the bootstrapping procedure (resampling technique) in Smart PLS with 5000 samples involving 29 variables. Thus, for values above 1.96, for Student’s t-test, standard error (O/STDEV) and p-value less than or equal to 0.05, the relationships are significant.

Table 3. Test of significance of the hypothesized relationships

	H	β	STDEV	t	p	R	R ² ajustado	VIF
Assistência_Modelagem -> Compromisso_Afetivo	H1a +	0,208	0,072	2,884	0,004	0,391	0,387	1,736
Encorajamento_Suporte -> Compromisso_Afetivo	H2a +	0,470	0,074	6,330	0,000			
Assistência_Modelagem -> Compromisso_Normativo	H1b +	0,363	0,058	6,229	0,000	0,417	0,413	1,736
Encorajamento_Suporte -> Compromisso_Normativo	H2b +	0,348	0,064	5,469	0,000			
Compromisso_Afetivo -> Atitude_Sucesso	H3a +	0,315	0,074	4,282	0,000	0,498	0,494	2,43
Compromisso_Normativo -> Atitude_Sucesso	H3b +	0,434	0,077	5,663	0,000			
Atitude_Sucesso -> Intenção_Sucesso	H4 +	0,775	0,034	22,772	0,000	0,601	0,599	1,0

Source: Research data.

Legend: β = structural coefficient; STDEV = standard error; t = student’s t; P= p-value; VIF = variance inflation fact.

Note. With the Bootstrapping result, all factor loadings showed significance (t-values greater than 2.887).

To analyze the collinearity, one should observe the value of the variance inflation factor (VIF), which was between 1.0 and 2.43, that is, smaller than 5 (Hair Jr. et al., 2017). Regarding the explanatory capacity of the model, one has as a parameter the structural coefficient (R^2), with values ranging from 0 to 1, representing by $R^2=2\%$, small effect, $R^2=13\%$, a medium effect and $R^2=26\%$, a large effect (Cohen, 1977). With this parameter, it is observed that all the effects of the tested relationships are higher than $R^2=26\%$, while assuming important explanatory capacity in relation to the proposed model.

To analyze the direct effects of the predictor latent variables, the blindfolding technique was performed by means of a specific module in SmartPLS. The analysis of this effect defines relative importance of the predictor, about Cohen (1977) and Hair et al. (2014), which define (f^2) of 0.02, 0.15 and 0.35 considered small, medium and large, respectively.

Table 4. Relative importance (f^2)

	SSO	SSE	$Q^2(=1-SSE/SSO)$
Assistência_Modelagem	1734	686,652	0,604
Atitude_Sucesso	1445	583,792	0,596
Compromisso_Afetivo	1445	537,965	0,628
Compromisso_Normativo	1156	622,308	0,462
Incentivo_Sucesso	867	212,992	0,754
Intenção_Sucesso	1734	344,584	0,801

Source: Research data.

Note. Data extracted from the Blindfolding module (SmartPLS), while f^2 represents the Communality reading (cross-validation on construct communality).

With support in Table 4, which presents Cohen's indicator, or effect size (f^2), also evaluated by the ratio between the part explained by the model and the unexplained part ($f^2 = R^2 / (1 - R^2)$), after analyzing the output of the blindfolding module in relation to the validation of communalities, it is observed that all predictors present effect (f^2) greater than 0.35, which defines a large prediction effect. Based on the effects (f^2), it is observed that the latent construct "Success Intention" is the most representative of the model.

In relation to the cross-validation of construct redundancy (Table 5), also obtained by the blindfolding module in SmartPLS, we obtained the predictive capacity of the model (Q^2), or Stone-Geisser indicator, in which the perfect model can be observed through $Q^2=1$, as defined by Hair et al. (2014).

Table 5. Predictive power or relevance (Q^2)

	SSO	SSE	$Q^2(=1-SSE/SSO)$
Assistência_Modelagem	1734	1734	
Atitude_Sucesso	1445	937,016	0,352
Compromisso_Afetivo	1445	1026,591	0,290
Compromisso_Normativo	1156	838,872	0,274
Incentivo_Sucesso	867	867	
Intenção_Sucesso	1734	847,324	0,511

Source: Research data.

Note. Data extracted from the Blindfolding module (SmartPLS), while Q^2 represents the redundancy reading (cross-validation of construct redundancy).

When Table 5 shows predictive relevance values ($Q^2 > 0$), the predictive accuracy of the study model is satisfactory, meeting the criteria established by Hair et al. (2014), regarding the evaluation of the model predictive relevance.

Finally, to evaluate the significance test of the hypothesized relationships (H1a, H1b; H2a, H2b; H3a, H3b and H4), through the bootstrapping procedure, the significance of the standardized coefficient (β = path coefficient) was evidenced, with t values > 2.887 . For t-test > 1.96 and p-value < 0.05 , the relationships are significant. Thus, all the proposed relationships (hypotheses) were found to have a positive and significant coefficient (at the 5% level, p-value < 0.05). From this evidence, the results supported the seven hypotheses of the study.

5. Discussion of Results

From the perspective of contributions to family succession through the Global University Entrepreneurial Spirit Students' Survey (GUESS), around the proposed model with constructs related to family support (parental), commitment, attitude, and succession intention, which satisfactorily revealed validity and reliability, explanatory capacity, relative relevance, and predictive capacity, it is possible to discuss the relationships proposed in the hypotheses validated in the study.

Regarding the hypotheses suggesting that instrumental assistance and career modeling influence affective commitment (H1a+; $\beta=0.208$; $t=2.884$; $p=0.004$), as well as verbal encouragement and emotional support also influence affective commitment (H2a+; $\beta=0.470$; $t=6.330$, $p=0.000$), both confirmed, it is evident, definitely, that family support (parental), operationalized by means of H1a+ and H2a+, has an important capacity to explain the variation of affective commitment ($R^2=38\%$). It is also observed that verbal encouragement and emotional support have greater influence in relation to the explanatory capacity of variation in affective commitment ($\beta=0.470$).

With the results of H1a+ and H2a+ it is discussed the particular relevance of family support in relation to affective commitment succeeding processes, which is derived greater potential for identity and career alignment as a result of the trust and sharing necessary for successor preparation (Davenport & Prusak, 1998; Terra, 2005; Treviño & Tapies, 2010), as well as skill and behavior development (instrumental assistance and career modeling) and positive self-perception regarding the ability to take over the business (verbal encouragement and emotional support) (Bandura, 1997; Turner et al., 2003). Thus, it is derived that the identification with the family business in face of the perspective of pride and convergence of interests and professional expectations of the successor (affective commitment) can be activated through family support, while the family contribution in relation to the perception of self-efficacy has particular relevance.

Regarding the hypotheses suggesting that instrumental assistance and career modeling influence normative commitment (H1b+; $\beta=0.363$; $t=6.229$; $p=0.000$), as well as verbal encouragement and emotional support also influence normative commitment (H2b+; $\beta=0.348$; $t=5.569$, $p=0.000$), were confirmed, while family (parental) support, operationalized through H1b+ and H2b+, has a large explanatory capacity for the variance of normative commitment ($R^2=41\%$).

According to H1a+ and H2b+, we understand that family support is even more relevant, since besides contributing to affective commitment, it also influences normative commitment. In this case, both instrumental support and career modeling ($\beta=0.363$) and verbal encouragement and emotional support ($\beta=0.348$) reveal close contributions in relation to normative commitment, suggesting that the set of cultural values internationalized by successors and the standards valued by the family impact (family expectations) the sense of obligation towards the family business (family orientation) (Dawson, Sharm, Irving, Marcus & Chirico, 2015), contributing to the succession process. It is defined, therefore, that the pro-business family culture can contribute with normative commitment, which, in association with affective commitment, add great influence on succession.

Regarding the proposed relationship between affective commitment and succession attitude (H3a+; $\beta=0.315$; $t=4.282$; $p=0.000$), as well as of normative commitment in relation to succession attitude (H3b+; $\beta=0.434$; $t=5.663$, $p=0.000$), were confirmed. Thus, commitment (affective and normative), operationalized through H3a+ and H3b+ assume important explanatory capacity for the variation of succession attitude ($R^2=49\%$), while normative commitment assumes greater influence ($\beta=0.434$).

While commitment involves energy that is mobilized toward a target (Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001), the results of hypotheses H3a+ and H3b+ discuss the relevance of the successor's commitment to the family business in the face of succession dynamics. Thus, the success that derives from this commitment (Sharma, 1997) can be explained by the mobilization of succession attitudes (positive personal evaluations regarding succession) in relation to the desire to contribute and associated feeling of pleasure (affective commitment), and moral obligation to take over the business considering the family culture values (normative commitment) (Dawson, Sharm, Irving, Marcus, & Chirico, 2015). With this, it is understood relevant investment for the strengthening of culture in family businesses and the associated values, while its differential can be derived from its contextual and historical particularities. In addition, mobilizing the sense of belonging to the historically established culture can contribute to the desire to continue the legacy of the founders.

Finally, the suggested relationship between succession attitude and succession intention (H4+; $\beta=0.775$; $t=22.772$, $p=0.000$), besides being supported, demonstrates the greater explanatory capacity of the variation of the predictor construct ($R^2=60\%$), compared to the other hypotheses of the study. In this case, the proposition of Linan and Chen (2009), in relation to entrepreneurial attitude being an explanatory antecedent of entrepreneurial

intention, in this study, was confirmed with the adaptation proposed by the Global University Entrepreneurial Spirit Students' Survey (GUESS), related to family succession. Thus, in relation to the intention of succession that has repercussions in concrete actions (behaviors) that successors undertake during the family business, these can be activated through succession attitudes, as a result of the positive evaluation in relation to the succession process in which they are manifested in the decisions of these actors. Thus, it is also understood that the family culture and the values expressed by the family, for being the result of cognitive, voluntary and conscious evaluation (Sharma & Irving, 2005), need information, which suggests particular importance for clear, objective and precise communication regarding the succession and the expectations of the family (and the founders) in relation to the successor, which a previous planning may favor.

6. Conclusion

Considering the scientific objective of investigating relationships between family (parental) support ("instrumental assistance and career modeling" and "verbal encouragement" and "emotional support") and organizational commitment (normative and affective), in the attitude of succession in a family business, as well as its relationship intending to succession, The constructs studied by the Global University Entrepreneurial Spirit Students' Survey (GUESS), in a survey conducted at a Federal University in Brazil, with 289 respondents, were operationalized. They were estimated by the Partial Least Squares Path Modeling [PLS-PM] method, with the support of SmartPLS software (version 2.0 M3 Beta). From the evidence of satisfactory fit indices in the structural model, the results supported the seven hypotheses of the study.

In the theoretical and methodological path chosen, it was possible to evidence the alignment that the family support (parental) provides the opportunity for commitment to the family business which, in turn, promotes a positive personal evaluation about succession (succession attitude) and, subsequently, permeates efforts to perform actions related to the family business (succession intention). Moving forward in the understanding, predictors with high explanatory power, validated in this study, provide favorable contributions to the succession process of family businesses. Thus, a reflexive and, why not, proactive "look" deserves to be highlighted by family businesses that are configured to overcome the challenges posed in this succession issue, especially regarding the preparation of their successor.

Considering the positive implication of family support in relation to the commitment succeeding processes, measures are suggested in favor of affective, personal and professional incentives, as well as the sharing of parents' practices, knowledge, experiences and life experiences, so that there is an affective commitment from future family members, since feelings of empathy, belonging, meanings and positive emotional values will be translated by the acceptance of the conduction of the family business.

Moreover, it is emphasized that the importance of the family culture and the values expressed by the family, through the parents' incentives regarding instrumental support, career modeling, verbal encouragement and emotional support, will be essential for this succession process, since the normative commitment, guided by obligation, loyalty, duty and guilt (in case they do not follow the family business), will be the driver for them to take over the family business.

Commitments secured, it is estimated that there will be a positive personal evaluation for the succession process. In this sense, the succession attitude will certainly be evidenced, because there is an identification of advantage (rather than disadvantage) in the successor career; besides being attractive, advantageous and timely, linked to the search for personal and professional satisfaction. In this path, the predisposition to assume the family business is conditioned to antecedent movements that involve effective actions to ensure the commitment of the successors, directly and positively linked to the parental support in this process.

In short, the resulting contributions lead to the understanding that the sustainability of family businesses is related to overcoming their challenges in the succession process. Thus, to (re)mean the family and organizational culture, built and instituted, can be a step for the successors to value the construction of the family business and feel prepared for the future managerial challenge. Therefore, a previous planning, with actions that mobilize the future family members (successors) can result in the longevity of these companies. It is credited, and thus, that perpetuation will be the driving force of economic and social development.

It is limited by the implication in a specific regional context, given the sample used, and by the choice of only one antecedent of the intention to succeed (in this case, the attitude of succession) in the construction of the theoretical model. However, suggestions for further studies are in the direction of replicating the structural model in other contexts, with the use of control variables in the model presented (multigroup modeling) such as; age, level of education, region of residence; besides the inclusion of new constructs in the theoretical model, such as; subjective norms and perceived behavioral control (antecedents of succession intention), and the formative

process of successors (entrepreneurial intention) as a predictor of succession intention.

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